

Correctional Institutions (Prison) Congestion and the Health Implication of Inmates in Nigeria

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Abstract

The compaction of inmates and the problem associate to it calls for urgent attention. Hitherto, the prison yards across the nation were built in accordance with the peculiar nature of criminal activities and criminal justice system. The overgrowing incidence of crime and the detention of offenders in the correctional service has led to the congestion of the prison. Hence, this paper is a theoretical research that attempt to re-emphasize and re-awaken the mind of the government and the entire humanity on the conditions of inmates in prison as with regards to Nigeria prison congestion and its health implications on inmate. This study therefore recommends among others that the federal/state government should ensure and take it as a point of duty and urgency to build more prison and the renovation of old ones across the country. Prison monitoring teams should be established without delay to monitor and supervise on regular basis inmate food, hygiene/sanitations, congestion and the general treatment to ensure observance of the United Nations standard minimum rule for the treatment of prisoners.

Keywords: prison, congestion, inmates, health condition and criminal justice system.

Introduction

Over the years, so much has been said about the deplorable conditions of the correctional service in Nigeria, particular on the adverse health implications on inmates due to congestion. This is a condition that successive government in Nigeria has been blamed of negligence instead of proffering long-lasting solution to this problem. Several measures and policies in decongesting prison population in Nigeria have been defined, yet the population of prison inmates continues to increase almost astronomically on yearly basis. Nigeria prisons houses both remand population which primarily constitutes a greater segments of the prison population. Remand prisoners, according to (Bright, 2016), are those awaiting trials male (ATM), awaiting trial females (ATF), convicted male (CM), convicted female (CF), debtors, criminal, lunatics, mentally ill persons charged with an offence and civil lunatics, mentally ill persons charged with no crime, condemned convicts (CC), prisoners on death row (PDR), lodgers and detainees from other prisons. To this end, Nigeria prisons tend to be congested because of the swelling population explosion by the facilities and infrastructure which have been overstretched with this population pushing, it has become an impossibility for presents facilities such as accommodation and medical services to adequately cater for the detainees in our prison who are in need of them (Ekwowusi, 2006 in Akpaneyene, 2007). In 2000, the panel reform institute (PRI) in Abuja, the Nigeria Capital, commended a major project to address many aspects of panel reform issues. These included, provision of prisoners with skills training, supporting prisoners families and advocating the argument for prisoners to be entitled to vote and be given

employment opportunity when they are released from prisons, here, the issues of congestion in prisons was highlighted and discussed.

In June 2012, the then minister of interior Chief Sunday Afolabi, said that the government would review prisons laws and prison reform, train personnel, rehabilitate inmates and re-strengthen the prison system to wear a new look with the view of addressing the problem of prison congestion. Furthermore, in 2006, the presidential committee on prison reform recommended improving the condition of service of prison and police officials and addressing the issues of prison congestion and the number of prisoners awaiting trials, when then president Obasanjo received the committee report, he respond by saying that the federal government would implement its findings.

In July, 2007, Amnesty International delegate visited ten (10) prisons in the federal capital territory (FCT), Enugu, Lagos and Kano state, the delegates also visited a psychiatric hospital in Enugu state which housed a bogus number of people with mental illness who had been transferred there from prison. In their report said Aster van Kretgen, at a press conference in Abuja that “the problems in Nigeria criminal justice system, especially its prisons are abysmal, so blatant and such that the Nigerian government has had no option but to recognize them, a situation of which successive government has pledged many time that it will reform the criminal justice system in general and the prison in particular. he added that “the Nigeria government is simply not complying with its national and international obligations when it comes to the criminal justice system reformation and that Nigerian must begin to do so seriously and urgently (Kresten, 2007).

Despite all efforts aimed at decongesting the prisons, it is still yet to be realized. What then are the hindrances or imbalances to prison decongestion? How does this affect the original plan of prison? It is in view of the above that the boiling questions set to be answered by this research and the major findings as to why prisons congestion in Nigeria still continue to resurface and to what extent does the congestion affect the health of inmates.

Literature review

The aims of Nigeria Prisons

Prison all over the world are officially and primarily set up by laws as a correctional institution to provide services where offenders of the law are sent to be punished, rehabilitated, reformed, through training in various skills to make themselves relevant after serving their prisons terms. It is also expected that the prison should reform inmates into self-respecting, law abiding and socially responsible citizens of a particular society. The Nigeria prison service (NPS) derive its operational power from CAP 366 laws of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1990 to perform the following responsibility of taking into custody all those who have been interred to correct them for eventual release and to help integrate them back into the society which are;

- a. To take into lawful custody all those certified to be so kept by courts of competent jurisdiction.
- b. To produce inmates in court as and when due if they are on remand.
- c. To identify the roots causes of inmates anti-social behaviour.

- d. To set in motion mechanisms and appropriate machinery for inmate treatment and return them back to the mainstream of society as normal law abiding citizens.
- e. Administer prison farms and industries for this purpose and in the process generate revenue for the state.
- f. To organize local and international seminars, workshops and conferences on human rights issues for public enlightenment and awareness.
- g. Maintain a library, collect data and disseminate information and educational materials on human rights generally.
- h. To house inmates in a more humane environment that is free from diseases and other social barriers to their well-being.
- i. To put in place the focal infrastructural development, inmates training and staff training and retraining (Ekwowusi, 2009 in Akpaneyen, 2010).

Prison congestion in Nigeria as a social problem

Over-crowding in prisons usually occur where the number of prisoners exceeds prison capacity to an extent inmates cannot be housed in a humane, healthy and psychological manner. In Nigeria, overcrowding is generally called congestion, perhaps, however, over the years, it has been widely acknowledged by individuals and Non-Governmental Organization locally and internationally that the Nigeria prison system has been bogged down by considerable challenges of congestions of inmates inspite of the heinous alarm raised by human right organization, it was gathered that most prisons yards in Nigeria are overcrowded beyond the actual initial capacity at which most prisons were

built for (Jofferson, 2010). This manifests in practical realm in most of the prisons holding more population of inmates as against the original capacity of inmates to accommodate, which in turn over stretches available infrastructure beyond their boundaries of function due to human pressure had been identified in notable Nigeria prisons.

For example, considering the act of imprisonment as the most effective form of sanction of offenders, nevertheless, in the last few decades, inmates population in Nigeria have grown substantially to the extent leading to the clustering and crowding of prisoners together in a choky cell, which tends to alter the psychological, physiological and behavioural well-being of the inmates (Crystal, 2011). The massive influx of inmates that begun in recent times as a result of delay in judiciary processes produces a rate growth and continuous rise in the nations inmates population that scholars and legal commentators have described and characterized as unprecedented.

Aduha (2009) reported that the total prisons capacity during the period of 1978 to 1981 was 27,257, but it was revealed that in 1978, the average monthly population was 32,332, in 1977 it was 34,477, in 1980, it was 35,332 and in 1981 it was 38,477 (Nigeria Prison Service 1999). The figures above portray a steady rise in 1981, overcrowding thus was 1961 in 1978, 27,56 in 1978, 29.43 in 1980 and 41.16 in 1981. In 1990, the average monthly population stood at 54,000 whereas the total capacity was 31,000 (Nigeria Prison Service, 1991). According to the annual abstract on statistics in 1999, no fewer than 482 of the 13,036 offenders were found to have been convicted six time or more, 758 were found to have been convicted five times 1,017 four time. 646 (641 men and five women)

three times 1,252 (1,237 men and 15 women), twice 2,598 (1,572 men and 26 women) while once 10,417 were first offenders. Nigeria has 148 prisons, ten (10) prisons farms and nine (9) cottage industries for the training of inmates. The actual capacity of the Nigeria prisons is 33,348 but the prisons currently holds 47,000 inmates, in May 1999, the prisons population was 40,899 of this number 21, 579 (52.8%)were awaiting trial prisoners while in another statistics of the Nigeria prisons service (November, 2001) estimate that the inmate population was put at 47,000 with awaiting trails constituting 24, 953 (59%) of the figure. The analysis shows that only about 30 of the nation's 231 regular and satellite prisons accounts for 50% of the country's total prisons population of which 22,609 in these 30 prisons, 16,461 are awaiting trial prisoners.

But more disturbing than the mere head court of inmate is the rate of growth relative to prison capacity, according to details obtained by news Agency of Nigeria (NAN) from office of the chief Judge of Lagos state in September 2012, shows that the Kirikiri medium prison built to accommodate 824 prisons inmates is hosting 2,402 inmates of which only 24 prisoners are convicted, Badagry with capacity of 160, has 215 inmates, Akwa prison in Anambra state has capacity for 98 inmates, Ogwash-Uku prison in Delta State against its 51 capacity representing 245% above capacity. Minna prison designed for 87 prisoners (170% above capacity, lapai prison also in Niger state has 161 inmates against its 60 capacities, Ilorin prison in Kwara state with 121 capacities has 199 inmates, Owerri prison in Imo State has 1,004 in a space meant for 548s, the five prison in Lagos state have an aggregate capacity of 2,665 but 5534 inmates are cramped in them. It was also reliably

gathered that of the 21,131 inmates in River State prison, 1,327 are awaiting trial. In Sokoto state 4,320 of the 873 inmates fall into this category, 397 of Ogun state prisons of 684 inmates are awaiting trial, 761 of the 1,301 prisoners in Akwa Ibom State , 716 of Borno State, 1,618 and 803 of Enugu state prison population of 1,306 also belong to the awaiting trail category. The nation (2010) also had it that they are shortage of bed spaces where only half of the inmates sleep on bed of which diseases is wide spread, cells are unclean and offer little ventilation resulting in unhealthy and dangerous sanitary condition. Yelodu,(1995) submit that prison detention conditions remain a major hash challenge and life threatening to inmates.

According to Odeyemi (2011), a deputy comptroller of prison stated categorically that it is difficult for a prison officer to train somebody who is awaiting trial in the prison because they have not been tried to prove they are guilty of an offence. The prison which is established as an institution for reformation and rehabilitation of inmates to train and prepare them for retry into the society has fallen shirts of its expected role (Coyle, 2001). congestion in Nigeria prison is therefore basically a social ill as all units of the society are in one way or the other involved.

According to John (2013), a social problem is considered to be a situation that is incompatible with the values of a significant number of people in the society who agree that action is needed to alter the conflict condition in society. He went further to posit that, for a situation to constitute a social problem, it must first exist and draw the attention of the public and such a social condition must contradict the values of the people to whom it

constitutes as much as affecting the lives of significant proportion of people. He added that such a condition must be one that calls for urgent action geared towards remedying the situation. Prison congestion in Nigeria is therefore social problem because it calls for immediate action in order to resolve the ugly situation, which is also troublesome to a significant proportion of people. Urgent effort is therefore needed to address this problem.

Over-crowding in Nigerian prisons is also a social menace because it rises or increases government spending on prisons with a drop in government spending on education, agriculture, health and infrastructural development. Varness (2008) took a step further to say that any country adding to its prisons population will have to spend more money there and less money for other purposes or sectors. Research also had it that there is a subculture within the prison walls where inmates are socialized or enculturized to deal with the deprivation of prisoners (Ukwayi), it has been recognized that just as there is a culture among citizens in the normal and free world separate culture also exists within prisons walls called prisons community (Donal, 1998 and greshman Silkesis 1999) the concept portray the culture as the assimilation process in prisons where inmates take on in greater or less degree the folkways, mores, customs and general processes of socialization and assimilation in communities at large. Inmates are advised to adapt to the self-contained community of a prison.

However, since the values of the prisons are discordant with societal values, prisoners readjust and learn new norms, rules and the expected pattern of behaviour known as the “inmates’ code”. In light of the above what is considered unacceptable in the free

world may be encouraged and even rewarded inside the walls of the institution (prisons), with this, there is a high likelihood that when inmates with different degree of offences are grouped together, one group is bound to have a higher influence over the other and such influence might past a negative outcome on the inmates, in that when the first degrees of offender are released, they would bring to bear what they have learnt at the prison from their former colleagues, thereby causing more problems to the society.

Reasons for prisons congestion in Nigeria

In light of this research work a closer examination of the processing of prisons within the Nigerian criminal justice system and the various stages/phases will give some indications as to the reasons why Nigeria prisons are highly congested or over-crowded (Siegel, 1998).

- **Delay in the administration of justice**

According to Ukwayi (unpublished Lecture notes on administration of justice criminal justice) is the appropriate way and manner criminal cases charged before a courts, tried and disposed off by the law courts,.

i. Primarily, the police, courts and the prisons therefore constitute the tripod on which Nigerians criminal justice system stands. The police often normally play a very critical and crucial role that carries a multiplier effects on the other two (2) institutions. they function as the first gate keeper to these two agencies and by implication what they let in or out, the courts and prisons can then predispose themselves to act on them or stay action.

Unfortunately, the police now constitute a serious clog in the wheel of criminal justice in that various police divisions across the country do arrogate to themselves the power of judges and magistrate in determining who goes to courts, who remains indefinitely in prisons or cell or who regains freedom when the right amount allegedly exchange hands. Research also show cases where police officers indiscriminately dumped various citizens in police cells into prisons in order to decongest their cells for fresh intake, torture by police is also routine and widespread, with torture often used as evidence in trial, while other category simply due to their case files having been lost by the police, remains in the prisons while other category simply due to their case files having been lost by the police, remains in the prisons for no reason but common offences such as theft, assault, traffic violation and unlawful possession which together account for 53% of prison population between 1999 and 2007. The police do not adhere or rather respect section 34 sub-section (1a) which says police should bring a suspect promptly before a judge or judicial officer within 24 hours, but in the case of the police it usually takes weeks if not months before suspect are brought to courts after a enough torture to extract information from the suspect.

ii. Courts: In the administration of justice, the courts are to take over from where the police stopped, in that when a crime is committed by any suspect , investigation are conducted which may lead to the arrest of a suspect or group of suspects for interrogation, then the suspect would further be “processed” to determine whether or not there is a case to answer. Thereafter, the suspect(s) file is sent to the Director of Public Prosecution (DPP)

for scrutiny and critical analysis before the suspect is finally charged to courts to determine his/her fate. Courts all over the world are established to be impartial arbiters in legal disputes involving individuals and groups. This adjudicatory function is the *raison d'être* of courts. The common saying that “everybody is practically equal before the law is an indication that in their judgment the courts strive to maintain justice and fairness regardless of the socio-economic status of those arraigned before them. As vital and pivotal their function is in the administration of criminal justice, the courts have failed to ensure that all inmates brought before them are tried within reasonable time. This behaviour performed with all level of technicality by the courts pose a serious threat and problem to inmates. This was gathered from prisons sources which is traceable to ineptitude of the use of adjournments as a tool usually employed by some members of the courts with the name of investigation to delay justice, thereby causing a person to be committed into prison as awaiting trial inmates which causes a huge dilemma in inmates rights (Ewelukwa, 1990). It is beyond doubt that when more than 60-65% of the total prison inmates are awaiting trail, it therefore means that the administration of criminal justice must be faulty and confused (Aduba, 1993). He further identified several other factors responsible or militating the delay in the administration of criminal justice in Nigeria. First, the inadequacy of the courts and judicial personnel, it is an obvious fact that in Nigeria, the increase in population in some major urban cities has brought about high level of crime rate and this has not been matched with corresponding increases in the number or size of courts buildings.

It is also widely agreed today that the numbers of countless adjustments of cases in courts due to argument between members of the bar or mis-matching of findings have made a mess of our justice delivery system, a situation that made the criminal justice in the country to be accused of causing prisons congestion through the consistence and persistence delay of suspects (awaiting trial person) on a protracted court process (Amnesty International, 2010). Furthermore, findings often are not completed on time because the law is unduly technical, inconsistent and more significantly, the public is very reluctant to assist the law enforcement agents such as the police, civil defence corps, EFCC, ICPC, NDLEA, NAFDAC etc. with useful or needed information to facilitate investigation due to past experience (Oshode and Morgan, 2012).

Delay also occur in criminal appeals because of the indifferences and incompetence of secretarial staffs, records of proceedings which may be spread throughout many records books, frequent transfers of magistrate which makes it difficult for them to compile recorded of officials (Aduba, 1993). All of the above vis-à-vis in one way or the other contributes immensely to the over-crowding, especially in relation to the figure of awaiting trial persons.

- **Government inability to established jails**

Another major impediment to prison over-crowding is the inability of government to separate main prisons from jail also gives credence and confidence to congestion of prisons in Nigeria. Jail as it is used here is a place for housing offenders awaiting trials for various crimes, by designation, research shows that jails are locally operated by local

council or by private cooperation's or bodies in advance countries, but in the case of Nigeria, all degree of offenders are sent to prison custody which freely hip over-crowded of prisons (Oshodi, 2012). He further noted that the prison claim that keeping or taking custody of awaiting trial person is not strictly part of their constitutional duty.

- **Overuse of prison sentence by judges**

There is also the prove of overuse of imprisonment as a means of punishment with aggrieve party, in that about one-third of the convicted prisoners in Nigeria are incarcerated for stealing without violence, about 80% are serving not more than two years of imprisonment and that 55% are first time offenders (Amnesty International, 2010). The research further show the presence of debtors, mentally disordered persons and pregnant and nursing mothers, a situation whereby most inmates in these prisons were remanded in prison on flimsy charges and in some cases on no charges preferred against them, it was observed that 60% of the inmates have spent between 2 to 4 years incarcerated, 20% between 4 to 6 years, 10% between 8 to 11 years and another 10% between 9-12 years also among the inmates are aged, (60-65yrs), the juvenile inability to raise the amount allegedly demanded by the investigating police officer (IPO) and prosecutors while they were under police custody.

- **Inability of government to build additional prisons**

Most of the Nigerian present prisons were built during the colonial era and since then, very little zeal or appetite has been made by the government to build additional prisons or to refurbish the existing ones (Oshodi, 2012). He took a step further to say that

with the increases in prisons admission because of high crimes rate in recent times in the form of terrorism, kidnaping, child trafficking bombings, it is only Akwa Ibom state government that have been able to build a new prisons yards for inmates among the 36 states government within the last decade (Oshodi and Michael, 2012).

Implication of prisons congestion on inmate's health

It is a common knowledge that the effect of Nigeria prisons congestion and having overpopulated undeliverable number of inmates make the Nigeria prisons as a reformatory institution, a ground for developing psychological, physiological and mental health as well as physical ailments or disadvantages (Egba, 2011). He went further to say that, it is a fact that the increasing and shifting number of mentally ill persons has continues to contribute to congestion of the courts and consequently the poison. Yet, the federal government continues to have no clear intention of removing the severely mentally ill inmates from the overburdened prisons. According to (Amnesty International, 2008), the appalling prison conditions in Nigeria prisons, including the severe over-crowding are seriously damaging the mental and physical health of thousands if not millions of inmates. The report also reveals that with the ensuring congestion, most prisoners sleep on the floor and are provide with minimal food ratios. A condition he explained has not only overstretched the facilities to breaking point. But it also a contributing factor to prison breaks nationwide due to the maltreatment and lack of medical care. And that over-crowding and poor sanitation leads to high incidence of diseases such as a skin infections, malaria. Tuberculosis, diabetes. Scabies, dysentery, cannabis, viral hepatitis, A-E, arthritis, (13%) kidney problem (4%),

HIV/AIDS also about 34% of inmates were reported to have some kind of physical impairment, including learning, speech, hearing, vision or mobility impairment, high blood pressure cases were (9.8%)m mental health disorder with affective disorders and schizophrenia (13.9% and 2.0% respectively). Typhoid, cholera, food poisoning and pneumonia, suicide as a result of frustration and unprecedented hardship, diarrhea and loss of appetite as a result of constant torture and other practices that undermine human development and self-actualization, in most prisons particularly Afokang prison calabar, were the small sick bays lack medicines and in most instances inmates have to pay for their own medical care, frequent demand of bribes from inmates by guards for them to receive visitors, contact their families and being allowed outside their cell at all. Hassan (2010) maintained that the primary causes of health challenges that inmates develop in Nigeria prisons are based on congestion, unsanitary environment, malnutrition and exposure to cold or heat in the cells. These are a testament to prove the fact that prison over-crowding results to ill health of inmates.

Other numerous factors that explain the vulnerability of the population to health implication are high-risk sexual practices, sexual abuse, rape, homosexuality, injecting drugs, sharing unsterilized needles and syringes, sharing of razor blades, overcrowding and cramped conditions and poor health facilities. That the Nigerian government failed to recognize or address the disease unethical and social health implication in the prisons does not mean they do not exist.

Theoretical framework

Rehabilitation model

This model was propounded by Micheal Foucault in 18th century (Lurt, 2001). It holds that over time, prison have combined elements of punishment with elements of rehabilitation. According to Foucault (1857), punishment shifted over time from the disciplining of the “body” to the disciplining of the “soul”, the rehabilitation of offenders is a key feature of the modern criminal justice system. Rehabilitation techniques vary according to the nature of the offence, the type of offence committed, and the institution in question (Moore, 1998). The punishment is believed to bring about a total restoration of the inmates in order to adjust and adapt to his/her environment.

Rehabilitation model is relevant to this study because it links inmate health conditions to the punishment given to the inmates. Thus, the kind of punishment given to the inmate may have a direct impact on the health condition of the inmate. For instance, in prison, inmates are been beaten and sent to congested prison cells as their punishment. This condition may inflicts injuries on the inmate’s body and perhaps lead to wide spread of diseases.

Conclusion

The intention of this research work was to examine Nigeria prison congestion and the health implication of inmates. Though several studies has been undertaken by concerned researchers to address this upsurge problem in the country which has indicated to be the reason for the inadequacies of the prison system as a corrective institution.

It will be impartial to allude that the Nigerian prison community is more punitive and dehumanizing than the supposed assigned corrective assignment it should be focusing on in the present global dispensation for the demand of human right in prisons. In practical reality, the relentless persistent of this problem has become a social ill and nightmare because it has deprived the prison inmates a sense of belonging and the much needed opportunity for reformation and rehabilitation of which the prison service was established.

This is so because as far as the economic system and the political terrain is poor and porous and people must eat to live, they will always no doubt alter or manipulate other means of survival that is favourable to them but against the norms and the appropriate social order of society. To realize the objectives of prison congestion the government should try as much as possible and plausible to implement the various recommendations cited in this work. it is hoped that modest contribution to policy makers, the government, judiciary and non-governmental organization (NGOs), to chart a more acceptable and reliable course “convenient” in making the Nigerian prison a more suitable and not horrible institution for reformation of inmates (prisons and known to be school for prisoners).

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study, the following recommendation are made;

- Imprisonment of a law breaker is expensive in terms of cost and the side effects are devastating as such investigation of suspect should be more extensive and thorough to avoid congestion in prisons.

- The criminal justice committee should be compelled to be more effective in utilizing their power of jail delivery to at least, a minimum of four times per year visit to decongest the prisons.
- At the prison level, communication and information on awaiting trial/remand prisoners independent and other monitoring mechanism should be improved
- Prison monitoring teams should be established without delay to monitor and supervise on regular basis inmate food, hygiene/sanitations, congestion and the general treatment to ensure observance of the United Nations standard minimum rule for the treatment of prisoners.
- The encouragement of active participation of the community in the rehabilitation of the inmates into the society after incarceration with the view to successfully integrating the inmates.
- One sure way of decongesting the Nigerian prisons is by adopting the alternative to imprisonment which includes community sentencing and supervision as in Zimbabwe which practices community involvement in sentencing as an alternative to imprisonment and Restorative Justice system.
- Government should ensure that programmes aimed at eradicating poverty and unemployment must be initiated and implemented to the latter, because completion and struggling for scarce resources usually serves as a gate way in committing crime.

- The federal/.state government should ensure and take it as a point of duty and urgency to build more prison and the renovation of old ones across the country.
- There should be a right to sleep on a mattress and medical services because a situation where inmates sleep in turns on the bare floor like sardines and animal meant for slaughtering is a disgrace to humanity.

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